

THE HUMAN COST OF WAR: MIGRATION, DISPLACEMENT, AND HUMAN RIGHTS IN THE BLACK SEA REGION

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ABSTRACT

The human cost of war is evident in the profound displacement and migration caused by armed conflicts, with significant implications for human rights. This article examines the impact of war on migration and displacement, focusing on Ukraine and Turkey within the Black Sea region. Both countries have been central to recent geopolitical tensions, with the ongoing war in Ukraine and Turkey's role as a host for millions of refugees, particularly from Syria. This study explores the legal and human rights challenges faced by displaced populations, highlighting the experiences of refugees and internally displaced persons from Ukraine and Syria.

The article also examines the rights of vulnerable groups, including women, children, and ethnic minorities, who are disproportionately affected by displacement. The challenges of legal enforcement and political complexities in both countries are explored, emphasizing the need for enhanced international cooperation and more robust legal frameworks to protect displaced populations.

In conclusion, this article provides insights into the legal and humanitarian challenges in Ukraine and Turkey, offering recommendations for improving protections for displaced persons and addressing the root causes of conflict to reduce the human cost of war.

Keywords: Forced migration, Displacement, Refugee law, Ukraine, Turkey.

SAVAŞIN İNSANİ BEDELİ: KARADENİZ BÖLGESİNDE GÖÇ, YERİNDEN EDİLME VE İNSAN HAKLARI²

ÖZET

Savaşın insanî bedeli, zorunlu göç ve yerinden edilme gibi yaygın sonuçlarında en açık şekilde görülmektedir; bu durum, insan haklarının korunması açısından ciddi sonuçlar doğurmaktadır. Bu makale, Karadeniz bölgesinde silahlı çatışmaların göç ve yerinden edilme üzerindeki etkisini, son yıllardaki jeopolitik krizlerin merkezinde yer alan iki ülke olan Ukrayna ve Türkiye bağlamında incelemektedir. Rusya'nın Ukrayna'ya yönelik kapsamlı işgali, ülkede kitlesel yerinden edilmelere yol açarken; Türkiye, başta Suriyeliler olmak

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² Türkçe Başlık, editör ekibi tarafından, İngilizce metinden tercüme edilerek eklenmiştir.

üzere, dünyanın en fazla mülteci barındıran ülkesi olmaya devam etmektedir. Buna ek olarak, Ukraynalı sığınmacıların sayısı da artmaktadır.

Bu çalışma, uluslararası insan hakları hukuku, uluslararası insancıl hukuk ve mülteci hukuku çerçevesinde, mülteciler ve yerinden edilmiş kişiler başta olmak üzere, zorla yerinden edilen nüfusların karşı karşıya kaldığı hukuki ve insani zorlukları analiz etmektedir. Özellikle kadınlar, çocuklar ve etnik azınlıklar gibi kırılgan grupların yerinden edilme süreçlerinde karşılaştıkları özgül risklere özel vurgu yapılmaktadır.

Makale ayrıca, her iki ülkede hukukun uygulanmasında yaşanan zorlukları, kurumsal kapasite eksikliklerini ve göçün siyasallaşmasını ele almaktadır. Zorla yerinden edilen nüfusların daha etkin şekilde korunabilmesi için uluslararası iş birliğinin güçlendirilmesi ve daha etkili hukukî mekanizmaların geliştirilmesi gerektiği savunulmaktadır. Sonuç olarak, bu çalışma, yerinden edilen kişilerin haklarını güçlendirmeye yönelik politika önerileri sunmakta ve yerinden edilmenin yapısal nedenlerinin ele alınmasıyla savaşın uzun vadeli insanî maliyetinin azaltılabileceğini ileri sürmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Zorunlu göç, Yerinden edilme, Mülteci hukuku, Ukrayna, Türkiye

1. Introduction

Armed conflict has long been one of the primary drivers of forced migration and displacement. In recent years, the Black Sea region has emerged as a focal point of complex humanitarian crises, with Ukraine and Turkey playing central roles. Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 triggered one of the largest refugee crises in Europe since World War II, resulting in millions of IDPs and refugees fleeing across borders. Simultaneously, Turkey remains the world's largest host of refugees—primarily from Syria, but also from Afghanistan, Iraq, and more recently Ukraine—situating it at the nexus of regional migration governance.

The human cost of war extends beyond the battlefield, manifesting in the loss of homes, disruption of livelihoods, erosion of rights, and enduring psychosocial trauma. This article examines the legal, humanitarian, and political challenges posed by displacement in the Black Sea region, with a focus on Ukraine and Turkey as critical case studies. These countries highlight two key dimensions of war-induced displacement: Ukraine as a source of large-scale internal and cross-border displacement, and Turkey as a host state with complex domestic and international legal obligations.

The analysis is framed through the lens of international human rights law, international humanitarian law, and refugee law. Key instruments such as the 1951 Refugee Convention, the Guiding Principles on Internal Displacement, and regional mechanisms such as the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and the EU-Turkey Statement of 2016 are considered. The article also explores how legal frameworks interact with political realities on the ground, especially in contexts of prolonged conflict and fragile state institutions.

This study aims to:

- Assess the legal frameworks governing displacement in Ukraine and Turkey;
- Identify the primary human rights challenges faced by displaced persons;
- Highlight the vulnerabilities of specific populations, including women, children, and minorities;
- Examine the efficacy of national and international responses;
- Provide policy and legal recommendations to strengthen the protection of displaced populations.

By analyzing the lived experiences of displaced persons and the state responses in Ukraine and Turkey, this article seeks to contribute to the scholarly and policy-oriented discourse on the legal dimensions of forced migration in conflict zones.

2. International Legal Framework for Displacement

The phenomenon of war-induced displacement is governed by several intersecting branches of international law, each offering specific legal protections for displaced persons. These include international human rights law, international humanitarian law, and refugee law. Together, they form a comprehensive, though often fragmented, framework for addressing the rights of refugees, asylum seekers, and IDPs affected by armed conflict. In the context of the Black Sea region—particularly Ukraine and Turkey—these legal instruments provide both a moral imperative and a legal mandate to protect vulnerable populations.

International human rights law serves as a foundational element in the protection of displaced persons, guaranteeing core rights that apply universally. Instruments such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948), the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR, 1966), and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR, 1966) affirm essential entitlements: the right to life, the prohibition of torture and inhuman treatment, freedom of movement, and the right to seek asylum. These rights are not extinguished by displacement or the outbreak of conflict. In fact, they become even more critical under such conditions, when state protection often diminishes or disappears altogether.

Closely intertwined with human rights law is international humanitarian law (IHL), which regulates the conduct of armed conflict and offers protection to civilians, including those displaced by war. The Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their Additional Protocols form the cornerstone of IHL. They mandate humane treatment for all persons affected by hostilities and strictly prohibit forced displacement, except when justified by imperative military necessity or the security of the civilians themselves. The law of armed conflict recognizes the inherent vulnerability of displaced populations and imposes obligations on both state and non-state actors to minimize civilian harm.

Whereas human rights and humanitarian law apply broadly, international refugee law focuses more narrowly on individuals who cross borders due to persecution, conflict, or generalized violence. The 1951 Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees and its 1967 Protocol provide the definitional and normative framework for refugee protection. The Convention establishes the principle of non-refoulement, which prohibits the return of a refugee to any territory where they may face serious threats to life or freedom. This principle is a cornerstone of refugee protection and has been interpreted by courts and international bodies as a norm of customary international law.³

In addition to global instruments, regional mechanisms play an important role in shaping legal responses to displacement. The European Convention on Human Rights, adopted by the Council of Europe, has been pivotal in safeguarding the rights of displaced persons within the region. The Convention guarantees civil and political rights such as the right to life, the prohibition of torture, and the right to liberty and security. Through the jurisprudence of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), these provisions have been interpreted to protect refugees and asylum seekers from arbitrary detention, collective expulsion, and deportation to unsafe territories.⁴

One of the most consequential developments in regional migration governance is the EU-Turkey Statement of 18 March 2016. Designed to curb irregular migration flows across the Aegean Sea, the agreement stipulates that all new irregular migrants crossing from Turkey into Greek islands would be returned to Turkey, in exchange for resettlement of Syrians from Turkey to the EU on a one-for-one basis. In return, the EU pledged financial aid to Turkey, accelerated visa liberalization, and revitalized accession negotiations. However, the agreement has been heavily criticized for its human rights implications, particularly with regard to procedural safeguards for asylum seekers and the potential violation of the principle of non-refoulement.⁵

Together, these legal frameworks constitute a robust—yet unevenly applied—system of protection for displaced persons. While the normative standards are well-established, their implementation on the ground often falls short due to political constraints, lack of resources, and insufficient enforcement mechanisms. The following sections will examine how these international norms are interpreted and operationalized in the specific contexts of Ukraine and Turkey, offering a closer look at their respective legal responses to displacement and migration.

³ UNHCR. The 1951 Refugee Convention. Geneva: UNHCR, 1951. <https://www.unhcr.org/about-unhcr/overview/1951-refugee-convention>

⁴ Council of Europe. European Convention on Human Rights. Strasbourg: Council of Europe, 1950. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/human-rights-convention>

⁵ Council of the European Union. “EU-Turkey Statement, 18 March 2016.” Brussels: Council of the European Union, March 18, 2016. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2016/03/18/eu-turkey-statement/>

3. Ukraine: Displacement and Protection Challenges

The war in Ukraine has generated one of the most profound displacement crises in recent European history, with repercussions far beyond its borders. As the conflict persists, millions of Ukrainians have been uprooted from their homes, resulting in a complex landscape of internal displacement and cross-border refugee flows. The legal and humanitarian dimensions of this crisis reveal both the resilience of international legal frameworks and their limitations in responding to protracted, large-scale displacement.

By the end of 2023, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) estimated that more than 6.3 million Ukrainians had fled abroad, with the majority seeking refuge in Europe. Simultaneously, around 3.7 million individuals remained internally displaced within Ukraine's borders.⁶ The International Organization for Migration (IOM) reported an even higher number of IDPs—approximately 5.1 million—underscoring the fluid and often imprecise nature of displacement statistics in conflict zones.⁷ These numbers reflect not only the physical toll of war, but also the social, economic, and legal upheaval experienced by millions of individuals and families.

To respond to the needs of IDPs, Ukraine has adopted a legal framework aimed at ensuring basic rights and entitlements. The Law of Ukraine “On Ensuring the Rights and Freedoms of Internally Displaced Persons” outlines the procedures for registration and assistance, including access to social benefits, housing, and employment support. Despite this legal infrastructure, implementation has proven inconsistent. Bureaucratic inefficiencies, funding shortages, and continued military hostilities have all limited the law's practical effectiveness. Many IDPs remain in temporary or substandard housing, and the psychological burden of displacement—combined with economic insecurity—poses a significant challenge to integration and stability.

Outside Ukraine, the refugee response has largely been shaped by European solidarity, albeit uneven in its execution. In an unprecedented move, the European Union activated the Temporary Protection Directive in March 2022, offering Ukrainians immediate access to residence permits, labor markets, healthcare, and education across member states. This measure has provided critical relief for millions, while also sparking debates about the future of asylum policy and burden-sharing mechanisms within the EU. Countries like Poland, Germany, and the Czech Republic have absorbed the largest numbers of Ukrainian refugees, placing immense pressure on local infrastructure and services.⁸

⁶ UNHCR. Ukraine Situation: Global Report 2023. Geneva: UNHCR, 2023. <https://reporting.unhcr.org/ukraine-situation-global-report-2023>

⁷ International Organization for Migration. “Need for Financial Assistance Grows as 5.1 Million People Remain Internally Displaced across Ukraine.” Geneva: IOM, April 9, 2023. <https://ukraine.iom.int/news/need-financial-assistance-grows-51-million-people-remain-internally-displaced-across-ukraine>

⁸ Statista. “Number of Ukrainian Refugees Worldwide as of January 16, 2025.” February 2025. Accessed April 9, 2025. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1413699/ukrainian-refugees-worldwide/>.

Although the directive has alleviated immediate concerns, it is not a permanent solution. Legal scholars and humanitarian actors have raised concerns about the sustainability of temporary protection, particularly in the face of protracted displacement. Questions surrounding long-term residency, family reunification, and access to durable housing remain unresolved. Additionally, disparities in how the directive is implemented at the national level have led to inconsistent experiences for refugees, with some receiving robust support and others encountering bureaucratic delays and limited access to essential services.

The humanitarian consequences of displacement are acute and multifaceted. Internally displaced persons within Ukraine frequently face limited access to healthcare, education, and employment. Economic precarity is widespread; IOM assessments have shown that a significant majority of IDP households live below the subsistence minimum. Vulnerable groups—especially women, children, the elderly, and persons with disabilities—are at heightened risk of exploitation, gender-based violence, and trafficking. In refugee-hosting states, while legal status may be clear under the Temporary Protection Directive, social integration is far more complex. Language barriers, credential recognition, and access to mental health services continue to impede the full inclusion of displaced Ukrainians into host societies.

Looking ahead, the prospect of return for Ukraine’s displaced population remains deeply uncertain. Although many refugees express a desire to return home, ongoing insecurity, the destruction of infrastructure, and the absence of basic services deter repatriation. UNHCR has emphasized the importance of voluntary, safe, and dignified return, but achieving this will require sustained international support for reconstruction, peacebuilding, and reconciliation. For many, local integration or third-country resettlement may be more viable options in the medium term, though these pathways also demand significant policy commitment and resource allocation.

The Ukrainian displacement crisis thus exemplifies both the strengths and the fragilities of the international protection regime. While legal mechanisms such as the Temporary Protection Directive have demonstrated remarkable adaptability, the broader challenge remains: ensuring that legal rights are not only enshrined on paper but realized in practice, especially for those most vulnerable to the enduring impacts of war.

4. Turkey: Host State and Migration Governance

While Ukraine stands as a prominent case of war-induced displacement, Turkey occupies a pivotal position as both a host country and a strategic actor in managing migratory flows across the Black Sea and Eastern Mediterranean regions. Over the past decade, Turkey has become one of the largest refugee-hosting countries in the world, primarily due to the protracted conflict in Syria, but more recently also as a transit or temporary refuge for those displaced by the war in Ukraine. Its unique geographic location—bridging Europe, the Middle East, and Asia—has placed it at the heart of regional migration dynamics, with significant legal and humanitarian implications.

The legal foundation for refugee protection in Turkey is both complex and distinct from that of many European states. Turkey is a signatory to the 1951 Refugee Convention and its 1967 Protocol; however, it maintains a geographical limitation, meaning it grants full refugee status only to individuals fleeing events in Europe. As a result, non-European asylum seekers—such as the millions fleeing Syria, Iraq, or Afghanistan—are not recognized as refugees under Turkish law, but rather are granted temporary protection or conditional refugee status under national legislation, notably the Law on Foreigners and International Protection (LFIP) of 2013 and the Temporary Protection Regulation of 2014.

The temporary protection framework established for Syrians allows for legal stay, access to basic services, and limited work authorization. As of early 2024, over 3.2 million Syrians were registered under temporary protection in Turkey.⁹ The LFIP also lays the groundwork for managing international protection claims, including those of non-Syrians and, more recently, Ukrainian nationals arriving after the outbreak of the 2022 invasion. While Ukrainians in Turkey have largely arrived through visa-free travel and are not subject to the same procedures as other asylum seekers, they still face legal uncertainty regarding their long-term status, particularly as temporary visas expire or as they seek access to employment and social services.

One of the most significant elements shaping Turkey's migration policy is the EU-Turkey Statement of March 2016, a political agreement intended to stem irregular migration to the European Union via the Aegean Sea. Under the agreement, Turkey committed to accepting the return of migrants from Greece who had crossed irregularly, in exchange for financial assistance from the EU and promises of resettlement quotas, visa liberalization, and revitalized accession talks. While the agreement initially led to a dramatic reduction in crossings, it has been widely criticized by human rights organizations for compromising asylum guarantees and leading to unlawful pushbacks and inadequate procedural safeguards for those returned.

From a legal perspective, Turkey's dual role as both a protective and restrictive actor in migration governance reflects broader tensions between humanitarian obligations and political pragmatism. On the one hand, its policies have enabled millions to access safety, education, and healthcare—often in the absence of comparable generosity from other regional actors. On the other, Turkey's migration management strategy has increasingly been shaped by domestic politics and international bargaining, particularly with the European Union. Migration has become a critical issue in Turkish electoral politics, with public sentiment often turning against refugees amid economic downturns and political polarization.

For displaced persons, this evolving landscape creates a precarious existence. While Turkey provides critical short-term protection, the prospects for integration or durable solutions are often limited. Work permits remain difficult to obtain in practice, and many refugees are employed informally, exposing them to exploitation and legal insecurity. Access to education

⁹ Presidency of Migration Management. Temporary Protection. Republic of Türkiye, Ministry of Interior. Accessed April 9, 2025. <https://en.goc.gov.tr/temporary-protection27>

and healthcare, although formally guaranteed under the temporary protection regime, is not always consistent across provinces, especially in areas with high refugee concentrations.

Vulnerable populations—including unaccompanied minors, women at risk, and survivors of violence—face additional hurdles in accessing protection. Human rights organizations have reported instances of refoulement, arbitrary detention, and inadequate legal representation for asylum seekers, raising concerns about compliance with international norms. Moreover, the growing securitization of migration discourse in Turkey has contributed to an environment in which displaced populations are simultaneously seen as victims and as potential threats, undermining their human dignity and legal protection.

Despite these challenges, Turkey remains a crucial case study in both the opportunities and limitations of regional migration governance. It has demonstrated a capacity to absorb large numbers of displaced people with relatively robust infrastructure, while also serving as a testing ground for migration diplomacy. As Turkey continues to negotiate its role in regional and international refugee policy, the long-term outcomes for displaced populations—especially those caught in protracted situations—will depend on the development of more stable legal pathways, stronger protections, and sustained international engagement.

5. Vulnerable Populations and Intersectional Risks

In the context of displacement caused by armed conflict, certain populations face heightened risks and compounded vulnerabilities due to their gender, age, ethnicity, disability, or legal status. While international refugee and human rights law recognize the importance of special protections for such groups, the practical implementation of these protections often falls short, particularly in complex and protracted crises like those in Ukraine and across the Turkish border.

Women constitute a significant proportion of displaced populations in both Ukraine and Turkey. The UNHCR estimates that women and children make up more than 80% of Ukrainian refugees in Europe.¹⁰ For many, displacement exacerbates existing gender inequalities and exposes them to increased risks of gender-based violence (GBV), including domestic abuse, sexual exploitation, and human trafficking. Conflict and flight often erode traditional protection mechanisms, and displacement camps or temporary shelters may lack adequate security, lighting, or gender-segregated facilities. Reports by Human Rights Watch and other organizations have highlighted numerous cases where women and girls, both in Ukraine and in host countries, experienced sexual violence with limited access to legal recourse or psychosocial support.

Turkey, despite hosting millions of displaced persons, also faces considerable challenges in addressing the needs of refugee and migrant women. Syrian women, for example, often struggle with barriers to employment, language acquisition, and legal literacy, which in turn limit their autonomy and access to services. Women working in informal sectors are

¹⁰ UNHCR. Ukraine Situation. UNHCR Global Focus. Accessed April 9, 2025. <https://reporting.unhcr.org/operational/situations/ukraine-situation>

particularly vulnerable to exploitation and abuse. Although Turkish law provides for services such as shelters for survivors of GBV, access is often impeded by bureaucratic procedures, cultural stigma, or lack of awareness.

Children also face unique risks in situations of displacement. In Ukraine, schools and other civilian infrastructure have been directly targeted or repurposed for military use, depriving thousands of children of their right to education. UNICEF has documented extensive disruption to schooling across Ukraine, with more than 5 million children affected by school closures, displacement, or trauma.¹¹ For children who flee the country, the situation remains precarious. Though the EU’s Temporary Protection Directive guarantees access to education, the transition into foreign school systems poses difficulties in terms of language, curriculum, and social integration.

Unaccompanied and separated children are especially vulnerable to trafficking, abuse, and neglect. According to Europol and Frontex, there has been a sharp increase in the number of unaccompanied minors arriving in EU member states from Ukraine and other conflict zones. Their legal status is often unclear, and child protection systems in receiving countries are sometimes overwhelmed or underfunded, resulting in gaps in guardianship, housing, and psychosocial care.

Ethnic minorities—particularly Roman communities in Ukraine—face multiple layers of discrimination both during displacement and in host countries. Roman individuals are frequently excluded from public services due to lack of documentation, residence permits, or entrenched prejudice. In some cases, they have been denied access to shelters or humanitarian aid, as documented by Minority Rights Group International.¹² Similarly, non-Ukrainian nationals and stateless persons who were residing in Ukraine prior to the invasion have encountered unequal treatment when seeking asylum in Europe, raising concerns about racial bias in the enforcement of refugee protections.

The failure to adequately protect vulnerable populations in situations of displacement not only violates international obligations, it also perpetuates cycles of marginalization and trauma that can persist long after the initial crisis. Legal and policy responses must therefore adopt an intersectional lens, recognizing how multiple factors—such as gender, age, race, and socioeconomic status—interact to shape the experiences of displaced individuals. In both Ukraine and Turkey, progress depends not only on legal reform but also on a broader shift toward inclusive, rights-based approaches to displacement and migration.

¹¹ UNICEF. “War Has Hampered Education for 5.3 Million Children in Ukraine, Warns UNICEF.” Kyiv: UNICEF Ukraine, January 24, 2023. <https://www.unicef.org/ukraine/en/press-releases/war-has-hampered-education-53-million-children-ukraine-warns-unicef>

¹² Minority Rights Group International. “Roma Families Displaced by the War in Eastern Ukraine Face a Double Bind of Poverty and Discrimination.” Minority Rights Group, accessed April 9, 2025. <https://minorityrights.org/roma-families-displaced-by-the-war-in-eastern-ukraine-face-a-double-bind-of-poverty-and-discrimination/>

Persons with disabilities also confront severe obstacles in both Ukraine and Turkey. In Ukraine, the destruction of infrastructure and social services has left many disabled individuals unable to access necessary medical care, assistive devices, or evacuation routes. Human Rights Watch has documented cases in which disabled persons were left behind during evacuations or housed in facilities lacking accessible accommodations.¹³ In host countries, the lack of accessible housing and communication barriers further restrict the ability of disabled refugees to live independently or access their rights.

The situation of LGBTQ+ individuals also warrants attention. In both Ukraine and Turkey, members of the LGBTQ+ community often face discrimination and stigma, which are exacerbated in displacement contexts. LGBTQ+ refugees may be subject to harassment in camps or shelters, and often conceal their identities to avoid violence or exclusion.¹⁴ Legal recognition and protection for LGBTQ+ individuals vary widely between host countries, and many face difficulties accessing asylum procedures that account for their specific risks.

The intersectionality of these vulnerabilities underscores the need for a rights-based and inclusive approach to displacement. International instruments such as the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) provide normative frameworks that oblige states to ensure protection for marginalized groups. However, implementation at the national level is often hindered by resource constraints, lack of training among service providers, and sociocultural attitudes that perpetuate exclusion.

Ultimately, recognizing and responding to the differentiated impacts of displacement is not merely a matter of humanitarian policy but a legal imperative grounded in human rights law. The protection of vulnerable groups must be central to both emergency responses and long-term solutions. Without such an approach, efforts to mitigate the human cost of war will remain incomplete, and the principles of dignity and equality—so central to international legal standards—will be compromised in practice.

The legal protection of displaced persons in times of conflict is anchored in a triad of international legal regimes: IHL, international refugee law, and international human rights law. These overlapping systems offer a normative basis for ensuring the rights and dignity of refugees, IDPs, and other vulnerable groups. However, the practical implementation of these legal commitments—especially in complex contexts like Ukraine and Turkey—reveals significant disparities between legal obligations and enforcement realities.

In Ukraine, the domestic legal framework for internal displacement is grounded in the 2014 Law "On Ensuring the Rights and Freedoms of Internally Displaced Persons." This law,

¹³ Human Rights Watch. "Under Shelling in Kharkiv; People with Disabilities Need to Evacuate Safely." HRW, March 7, 2022. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2022/03/07/under-shelling-kharkiv>

¹⁴ OHCHR. "Ukraine: Protection of LGBTI and Gender-Diverse Refugees Remains Critical – UN Expert." United Nations, March 22, 2022. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2022/03/ukraine-protection-lgbti-and-gender-diverse-refugees-remains-critical-un>

enacted in response to the annexation of Crimea and the initial conflict in Donbas, guarantees IDPs access to social services, temporary housing, and employment assistance.¹⁵ While the legal basis is solid, enforcement has proven inconsistent due to several interlocking factors: underfunded institutions, bureaucratic inefficiencies, and the ongoing nature of military operations. Municipal authorities often lack the capacity or resources to fully implement IDP protections, especially in frontline or newly liberated territories where infrastructure has been damaged or destroyed.

Moreover, Ukraine's ability to uphold its obligations under international humanitarian law has been tested by the scale and brutality of the conflict. The targeting of civilian infrastructure, displacement of entire communities, and reports of war crimes—including forced transfers and attacks on hospitals and schools—raise serious legal concerns under the Geneva Conventions.¹⁶ Although Ukraine has cooperated with international monitoring missions and the International Criminal Court (ICC), ensuring accountability for these violations remains a formidable task amid ongoing hostilities and political constraints.¹⁷

Refugee protection in Turkey, by contrast, is shaped by its distinctive legal approach. As previously noted, Turkey maintains a geographic limitation to the 1951 Refugee Convention, meaning it grants full refugee status only to those fleeing events in Europe. For all others, including Syrians, Afghans, and many recent arrivals from Ukraine, Turkey applies either "temporary protection" or conditional asylum under the Law on Foreigners and International Protection (LFIP). While the LFIP is a relatively modern and comprehensive piece of legislation, its implementation has been hampered by institutional bottlenecks and shifting political priorities.

One of the most significant enforcement challenges in Turkey arises from the sheer scale of displacement. With more than 3.6 million Syrians and hundreds of thousands of asylum seekers from other countries, the Turkish Directorate General of Migration Management (DGMM) has struggled to process claims efficiently and ensure uniform standards across provinces.¹⁸ Reports of long waiting periods, inconsistent application of legal procedures, and limited access to legal counsel have emerged from various human rights organizations. In addition, administrative detention and deportations have raised alarms regarding the principle of non-refoulement, a core tenet of refugee law that prohibits the return of individuals to countries where they face threats to life or freedom.

¹⁵ Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine. Law of Ukraine No. 1706-VII 'On Ensuring the Rights and Freedoms of Internally Displaced Persons'. Kyiv: Verkhovna Rada, 2014. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1706-18>

¹⁶ Public International Law & Policy Group. "Are Russian Attacks on Ukraine's Electrical Grid a War Crime?" *Lawyering Justice Blog*, August 11, 2023. <https://www.publicinternationallawandpolicygroup.org/lawyering-justice-blog/2023/8/11/are-russian-attacks-on-ukraines-electrical-grid-a-war-crime>.

¹⁷ International Criminal Court. Situation in Ukraine. The Hague: ICC, 2022. <https://www.icc-cpi.int/situations/ukraine>

¹⁸ Human Rights Watch. "Submission by Human Rights Watch on Türkiye to the Human Rights Committee." *HRW*, October 23, 2024. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2024/10/23/submission-human-rights-watch-turkiye-human-rights-committee>

Enforcement is further complicated by the politicization of migration in Turkey's domestic landscape. As economic challenges have intensified, anti-refugee rhetoric has become more prevalent in political discourse, leading to periodic crackdowns and restrictive policy shifts. In some cases, refugees have been pressured to "voluntarily" return to Syria, despite ongoing risks—a practice criticized by international observers as coerced repatriation.¹⁹ Meanwhile, accountability mechanisms for abuses by state actors remain weak, and access to justice for refugees and asylum seekers is limited by language barriers, lack of legal aid, and social exclusion.

The international community, through institutions like the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR), and the International Organization for Migration (IOM), continues to support both Ukraine and Turkey in developing their protection capacities. However, the efficacy of such assistance is often curtailed by sovereignty concerns and the prioritization of national security or political stability over human rights obligations. For example, while the ECtHR has issued judgments related to the rights of displaced persons and refugees in both countries, implementation of its rulings remains uneven.

The broader challenge lies in the fragmentation of legal responsibility in protracted displacement settings. While the existing international legal regime provides important protections, it relies heavily on national implementation and political will. In both Ukraine and Turkey, legal frameworks are in place, but enforcement is undermined by war, political instability, administrative limitations, and at times, a lack of genuine commitment to rights-based governance.

Bridging the gap between law and practice requires a multifaceted approach: strengthening institutions, ensuring independent judicial oversight, enhancing transparency, and investing in the training of legal professionals and public officials. Most importantly, displaced persons themselves must be empowered to claim their rights—not merely as beneficiaries of humanitarian aid but as rights-holders under international law.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The human cost of war in the Black Sea region is starkly illustrated by the millions of individuals uprooted from their homes due to armed conflict, political instability, and geopolitical rivalries. From the devastating war in Ukraine to the protracted Syrian refugee crisis, which continues to have reverberations in Turkey, displacement has become a defining humanitarian and legal challenge of our time. As this article has demonstrated, while the normative frameworks of international law—humanitarian, human rights, and refugee law—offer a comprehensive system of protection, the realities on the ground frequently fall short of these legal ideals.

¹⁹ European Council on Refugees and Exiles. 2022 Update AIDA Country Report: Türkiye. Brussels: ECRE, 2022. <https://ecre.org/2022-update-aida-country-report-turkiye/>

In both Ukraine and Turkey, substantial efforts have been made to respond to large-scale displacement. Ukraine's legal architecture for internally displaced persons provides a crucial starting point for guaranteeing rights to those forced from their homes. Turkey, in turn, has adopted an ambitious national framework for international protection and has assumed a central role in hosting refugees within the region. Yet in both contexts, implementation remains a persistent challenge. Conflict conditions, institutional weakness, political pressures, and resource constraints often lead to gaps in protection, with vulnerable groups—women, children, minorities, persons with disabilities—bearing the brunt of systemic shortcomings.

Moreover, the increasing securitization of migration and the instrumentalization of refugees in political negotiations—such as the EU-Turkey deal—underscore the fragility of legal protections in times of geopolitical tension. When refugee and IDP policies are shaped primarily by strategic interests rather than legal obligations, the dignity and rights of displaced individuals are placed at risk.

To reduce the human cost of war and uphold the rights of displaced populations, a set of multi-level policy responses is needed:

First, states must strengthen domestic enforcement mechanisms. Legal frameworks must be supported by well-resourced institutions capable of processing claims efficiently, delivering social services, and ensuring due process. This requires investment in administrative capacity, training for public officials, and independent oversight to monitor rights violations.

Second, international cooperation must move beyond reactive and short-term approaches. Durable solutions—including voluntary repatriation, local integration, and third-country resettlement—must be pursued in a coordinated manner, with equitable responsibility-sharing between states. The EU and other regional actors should engage in principled partnerships with countries like Turkey, ensuring that legal standards are not compromised in the name of border control.

Third, the specific rights of vulnerable populations must be mainstreamed into displacement responses. Gender-sensitive and inclusive protection mechanisms, tailored education and healthcare programs, and anti-discrimination measures are essential for addressing the intersecting vulnerabilities faced by displaced persons.

Fourth, accountability for violations of international humanitarian and human rights law must be prioritized. In Ukraine, documentation of war crimes and forced displacement should be supported by international tribunals and transitional justice initiatives. In Turkey, safeguards must be enhanced to prevent arbitrary detention, refoulement, and violations of asylum rights.

Finally, addressing root causes of displacement—such as armed conflict, political repression, and economic deprivation—must be part of a long-term vision for regional stability. Conflict prevention, peacebuilding, and support for democratic governance are essential components of any strategy to reduce forced migration and uphold human dignity.

In sum, displacement in the Black Sea region represents a profound challenge to the international legal order and the values it seeks to protect. It calls for not only humanitarian concern but legal clarity, political commitment, and structural reform. By closing the gap between law and practice, states and international institutions can begin to respond more justly and effectively to the human cost of war.

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